

FEATURES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF KUNTUGMISH DOSTON

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10458525>

Annotatsiya

Ushbu tadqiqotda xalq og'zaki ijodi mahsuli bo'lgan "Kuntug'mish" dostoni, uning badiiy xususiyatlari hamda tarbiyaviy ahamiyati haqida fikr yuritiladi. Dostonning bosh qahramonlari Kuntug'mish va Xolbeka obrazlarining boshqalardan farqli jihatlari tahlil etiladi.

Annotation

In this research, the epic "Kuntug'mish", which is a product of folk oral creativity, its artistic features and educational significance is discussed. The characters of Kuntug'mish and Holbeka, the main characters of the epic, are analyzed.

Аннотация

В данном исследовании рассматривается эпос «Кунтугмиш», являющийся продуктом народного устного творчества, его художественные особенности и воспитательное значение. Анализируются характеры Кунтугмиша и Холбека, главных героев эпоса.

Epics are a type of folklore that is passed down from generation to generation. It is an artistic work of lyrical genre. In epics, historical reality is expressed in generalized images based on folk fantasy. Consequently, they are dominated by epic generalization. Such a generalization is based on the ideals and hopes of the people about social justice. So, epicness, monumentality, compositional and plot construction are characteristic of the epic covers complex events. It is known that the epic is a widespread genre in Uzbek folklore and classic literature, in which a specific event is narrated using the means of lyrical imagery. In it, the reality of life is widely covered, there will be one or two main characters, and there will be many secondary characters. The plot is lively and colorful, and the ideas of patriotism, heroism, humanitarianism, love, friendship, and loyalty are promoted in the minds of the readers. In the "Kuntugmish" epic, which is one of the best examples of Uzbek folklore, each character has its own role and even its name has a meaning. For example, Saint Karakhan's nickname is Qilichkhan, one of the kings of Nogai. Even though he

has been engaged in obedience and prayer for several years now, he considers justice, peace and satisfaction to be his main duty. Kuntugmish was given this name because he was the only child of Karakhan. The image of the poet's minister's daughter, Holbeka, is also a beautiful and courageous Uzbek girl, as intelligent as Tomaris, who values her self-worth highly, "the grain of her beauty came from Dagestan" (from the epic) a leech girl. Therefore, a person who decides to be his companion must be able to meet the requirements set by Holbeka. Of course, there are bad and cunning people in every era. Buvra Khan, the king of the time in the epic, after he realizes that Holbeka's condition is that he cannot win backgammon, he starts asking his ministers for advice, and with them they come up with a trick to enrich his happiness. In this way, he wants to reach Holbeka. The plot line consists of the suffering shown by Buvrakhan to Holbeka, who caused a lot of adventures in the epic, the image of Kuntugmish being put in a tulip (freshly slaughtered camel skin) and sent to the desert, and the lovers suffering from hunger and incapacity. In fact, Holbeka, like other girls, had the right to choose a suitable husband and build a happy life. But the tyrant king Buvrakhan's love for Holbeka, the lack of people who sympathize with Kuntugmish and Holbeka, the fear of the common people from the tyrant king, and the brutal punishment of those who tried to help can be understood from the image of the tyrants trying to easily decide the fate of people. In our opinion, social problems were added by every story teller and those who passed it on to the next generation before the appearance of this work and the current version. The missing Chilton and Mardon in the play also play an important role, that is, these chiltons are shown as mediators in the scenes that the main characters see in their dreams. The dream turns to the right, and the rings of the heroes are exchanged with each other. This event is the reason for the starting point of the love between the characters of Holbeka and Kuntug'mish, and with the help of chiltons, a feeling of love appears in the hearts of both of them. This pure love serves as a beacon for both heroes to overcome the trials and tribulations of life. Although there are many versions of this work, which is considered a purely romantic epic, the version narrated by the son of Ergash Jumanbulbul stands out for its relative perfection. In addition, the quatrains in the epic are also of special importance. In them, oppression and injustice are condemned and love, loyalty, loyalty and justice are glorified.

Og'ziga gap solsam, gapim olmaydi,
O'zbek ekan bilganidan qolmaydi,
Olib kenglar qirqin qizlar nardimni,

Ajal haydab kelgan ekan, bo'lmaydi.

Sinab ketsin nomardimni, mardimni,
Minib ketsin bedovimni, otimni,
Ajal haydab kelgan ekan, bo'lmaydi,
Olib kenglar, qirqin qizim, nardimni.

Rivoj bergin shahzodaning ishiga,
Yomon savdo kasod qilar kishiga,
Shahzodaga iqbol bergin, xudoyim,
Ko'p savdo solmagin yolg'iz boshiga.

Kosa olib sharob ichgan qirq chilton,
Xizir Ilyos pirim, yo shohi jahon,
Bu qizning qo'lida qo'yima sargardon,
Bu mushkul ishimni aylangiz oson¹.

Kuntug'mish epic is distinguished from other epics by its own characteristics. "Kuntug'mish" is a romantic-adventure epic, readers can think about patience, contentment, and most importantly, loyalty to one's neighbor. The image of women in the epic is also of special importance. For example, the image of Holbeka differs from the female characters in other folk epics by the fact that she is a female figure unmatched in intelligence, beauty and love throughout the entire epic. No matter how difficult the hero's trials are, he is able to overcome various trials and unite his family again until the end of the saga without giving in to despair. The image of Holbeka is considered the most beautiful example of the image of women in the Romanic epic. Because, like women in other romantic epics, she appears as a normal woman, not as a fairy or in a fantastical appearance. The image of Holbeka is embodied as a woman who has traveled the difficult spiritual path from being a lover to motherhood. Our attention is drawn to the fact that this image differs from other women with its determination and stubbornness that does not back down from anything. The most important thing is that she emphasizes her self-confidence and that she will not back down like brave young men, even though she is a woman. Holbeka, like Barchin, is a demanding, brave and brave girl. He competes with suitors. However, unlike him, Holbeka tries his hand at a game of backgammon with demanding suitors. In the Uzbek folk epic, such a test of a lover and a bride, a

¹ "Kuntug'mish" dostoni G'afur G'ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matba ijodiy uyi. Toshkent –2018. –B.37.

competition between a boy and a girl, can only be found in the "Kuntug'mish" epic.

As a conclusion, it can be said that no matter how hard the trials befall Holbeka, he is able to reunite his family at the end of the saga without giving in to despair. Holbeka appears not as a fairy or in a fantastical appearance like women in other romantic epics, but as an ordinary woman who can be close to reality. The image of Holbeka is embodied as a woman who has gone through a difficult spiritual path

References:

1. Haydarova, G. Traditions And Peculiarities Of Alisher Navoi In The Uzbek Ghazal Of The Xx Century. *The American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 2(13), 703.
2. Ahmadaliyevna, H. G. (2021). Talmeh or alluziya. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 772-779.
3. Аҳмадалиевна, Ҳ. Г. (2021). НАВОИЙ ВА СОБИР АБДУЛЛА. *ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI*, 1(2).
4. Ҳайдарова, Г. (2021). СОБИР АБДУЛЛА, ЧАРХИЙ ВА ҲАБИБИЙ ҒАЗАЛЛАРИДА ТАСВИР ВА ТАЛҚИН МАСАЛАЛАРИ. *FILOLOGIYA UFQLARI JURNALI*, 6(6).
5. Ahmadaliyevna, H. G. (2022). Interpretation of the Image of the Heart in the Poems of Habibi, Charkhi and Sabir Abdullah. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 6, 621-626.
6. Ҳайдарова, Г. А. (2022). XX аср ўзбек ғазалларининг вазн хусусиятига доир. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(6), 241-245.
7. Аҳмадалиевна, Ҳ. Г. (2022). СОБИР АБДУЛЛА, ЧАРХИЙ ВА ҲАБИБИЙ ҒАЗАЛИЁТИНИНГ ВАЗН ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИГА ДОИР. *Conferencea*, 47-49.
8. Гончарова, Н. В. (2023). ПРОБЛЕМА АНАЛИЗА И ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИИ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 5(NUU Conference 2), 275-279.
9. Goncharova, N. V. (2022). The Motive of Prayer, Passion and Gratitude in A. Kuprin's Novella " Garnet Bracelet" And S. Zweig's Novella " Letter of a Stranger. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(12), 19-22.
10. Кимсанова, М., Валиева, Ф., Пахриддинов, А., & Гончарова, Н. В. (2023, December). СПЕЦИФИКА АВТОРСКОЙ РЕЧИ ПОЭМЫ НВ ГОГОЛЯ «МЕРТВЫЕ ДУШИ». In *Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 92-98)*.

11. Vasilevna, G. N. (2023). THE EVOLUTION OF THE "LITTLE MAN" THEME IN THE RUSSIAN LITERATURE OF THE XX CENTURY. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 42, 287-291.
12. Попова, Е. И. (2022). Эстетическая Функция Грамматических Средств Языка В Художественном Тексте. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(11), 290-295.
13. Попова, Е. И. (2021). Контекстные основания транспозиции временных форм русского глагола. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(5), 150-155.
14. Попова, Е. И. (2018). Транспозиционные возможности употребления форм будущего времени. *Интернаука*, 12, 57.
15. Попова, Е. И. (2023). РИТОРИЧЕСКАЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКЕ УЧИТЕЛЯ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 42, 332-336.

